

Phytosterol Derivatives as Potential Antitumour Agents

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Several substituted urethane derivatives of β -sitosterol and stigmasterol as also their lauroyl esters were prepared as potential anti-tumour agents. On biological testing, none of the compounds, however, showed any activity.

β -SITOSTEROL, ('A', R=H), is a common phytosterol occurring in plants. In the antitumour screening of plant products, β -sitosterol appeared frequently as a constituent active against Walker carcinosarcoma 256. It has been shown to have some activity against Lewis Lung carcinoma and Murphy Sturm lymphosarcoma and marginal activity against Adinocarcinoma. Further, some more soluble derivatives of β -sitosterol viz. the hemisuccinate and carboxymethylthiohemisuccinate were prepared. Though these derivatives had better solubility than the original sterol and activity against Walker carcinosarcoma was retained, the therapeutic indices were not sufficiently high.¹ A survey of literatures showed that no other 'simple' sterol (i.e. excluding those with a lactone function) possesses *in vivo* or *in vitro* antitumour activity with the exception of estrone. Because β -sitosterol can be obtained from natural sources, we wanted to utilise it by converting into some suitable derivatives which might have better therapeutic indices.

Urethane and its derivatives have profound carcinostatic activity²⁻⁴. We, therefore, thought it desirable to introduce the urethane moiety in β -sitosterol as its substituted esters. Moreover, finding that certain fatty acids and their esters have significant carcinostatic activity⁵, the lauroyl ester of the sterol was prepared. Along with these, two derivatives of another plant sterol, i.e., stigmasterol (B, R=H) were also prepared. This paper describes the preparation of the sterol derivatives and the studies on their antitumour activities.

Chemistry: β -Sitosterol extracted from soyabeans was purchased from Sigma Chemical Co., U.S.A.. The product was further purified by column chromatography through silica gel to obtain a homogeneous pure sample of β -sitosterol which was used in subsequent experiments. Stigmasterol, purchased from Sigma Chemical Co., was also similarly purified and used. In the preparation of N-phenyl and N-p-Chlorophenyl urethanes, the sterols were refluxed with respective isocyanates in benzene for different lengths of time. The rest of the compounds were prepared by direct refluxing of the sterol in the reagents, thereby eliminating the use of solvent as a medium. The crude products were purified by column chromatography through silica gel and crystallised from suitable solvents. The compounds were characterised by their elemental analyses, infrared and ultraviolet spectra. The physical constants of the compounds are listed in Table-1.

TABLE-1

Compound	Melting point °C	% Yield	Mol. Formula	Carbon % :		Analytical Hydrogen % :		Nitrogen %		λ_{max} , nm	Specific Rotation [α] _D ²⁰ (In CHCl ₃)
				Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd	Found		
I	183-85°	61.06	C ₃₆ H ₅₆ O ₂ N	81.0	80.88	10.38	10.29	2.62	2.60	232	-26°
II	167.5°	77	C ₃₆ H ₅₄ O ₂ NCl	76.12	76.6	9.51	9.93	2.46	2.44	244	-28.57°
III	217-218°	42.4	C ₃₂ H ₅₅ ONS	76.64	77.1	10.98	12.7	2.794	2.84	246	-42°
IV	82-83°	66.8	C ₄₁ H ₇₂ O ₂	82.55	83.1	12.08	12.5	-	-	210	-11.9°
V	193-96°	64.2	C ₃₆ H ₅₈ O ₂ N	81.30	80.71	10.05	10.49	2.63	2.62	235	-42.8°
VI	93-95°	41.7	C ₄₁ H ₇₀ O ₂	82.81	82.3	11.7	12.2	-	-	210	-31°

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The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The ultraviolet spectra were measured in methanol solution with a Hilger spectrophotometer. The optical rotation was measured in chloroform in Hilger Watt's Polarimeter. The samples were dried *in vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide for microanalysis. The elemental analyses and infrared spectra were determined at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

N-Phenyl β-sitosteryl urethane (I). Phenyl isocyanate (17 ml., ~100m. moles) was added gradually to β-sitosterol (20.7g ; 50 m. moles) dissolved in 50 ml. dry benzene and the solution refluxed on a water bath for 10 hours. On cooling, the product deposited as solid, was filtered and washed with a little benzene and dried. The crude product dissolved in benzene was chromatographed through a column of silica gel (340 g). The fraction obtained in the benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) eluent was twice crystallised from a mixture of the same solvents.

M.P., 183-185° ; yield, 8.141g. ν in cm^{-1} : 2800

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$(\text{CH}_2)_n$; 1730 (-N-C-O) ; 1600 (aromatic) ; 1430 (C=C-H, δ -CH in plane) ; 1370-(C-CH₃) ; 1028 (eq. acyl group).

N-p-Chlorophenyl β-sitosteryl urethane (II). β-Sitosterol (4.14g. ; 10 m. moles). was dissolved in 25 ml. hot benzene and *p*-chlorophenyl isocyanate (3.07g ; 20 m. moles) in 5ml. benzene was added to it and the mixture refluxed on a water bath for 10 hrs. The solid, separated on cooling was filtered. The product was then chromatographed through a column of silica gel (200g.). The colourless solid obtained from the petroleum ether eluate on crystallisation from benzene yielded II. M. P. 167.5° , yield 4.35g. ν in cm^{-1} : 2941, 2857 (CH₂)_n ; 1724

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(N-C-O-) ; 1410 (-C=C-H, δ CH in plane) ; 1379 (C-CH₃) ; 1020-(eq.acyl gr.).

N-Ethyl β-Sitosteryl thiourethane (III) : β-Sitosterol (4.48g)~11m. moles), dissolved in a large excess of ethyl isothiocyanate (12 ml.) was refluxed for 50 hrs. The solid that deposited on cooling was filtered and washed with petroleum ether. The crude product, dissolved in benzene, was passed through a column of silica gel (160 g.). III was obtained in the benzene fraction and was crystallised twice with benzene. M.P. 217-218°. Yield, 3g. ν in cm^{-1} : 2941, 2857 (CH₂)_n ; 1563 (-C-N<), 1379, 1389

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(-C-CH₃) ; 1026, 1036 (eq. acyl groups).

N-Phenyl stigmasteryl urethane (V) : Procedure same as described in case of the compound I.

Crystallisation from petroleum ether gave V, m.p. 192-195°. Yield 4.09g. ν in cm^{-1} : 2800 (CH₂)_n ;

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1707(-N-C-O), 1600 (aromatic), 1430 (C=C-H, δ CH in plane) ; 1362 (C-CH₃) ; 1030 (eq. acyl group).

β-Sitosteryl laurate (IV) : 5 m. moles of β-sitosterol (2.07g) dissolved in lauroyl chloride (30 m. moles ; 6.6g) was heated on a water bath for 15 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and carefully poured on crushed ice. The solid separated was filtered and dried. The material was then extracted with petroleum ether and the extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After concentration, the solution was passed through a column of silica gel (60g).

Elution of the column with petroleum ether gave the desired product IV, which was crystallised from benzene-methanol mixture. m. p., 82-83°, yield 2.03g. ν in cm^{-1} : 2899(CH₂)_n ; 1750 (ester-CO-O-) ; 1380 (C-CH₃) ; 1032 (eq. acyl group).

Stigmasteryl laurate, (VI) : Procedure same as in case of IV. After elution through a column of silica gel, the product was crystallised from benzene ethanol mixture. M. P. 93-95° Yield : 64.2 g ν in cm^{-1} : 2857 (CH₂)_n 1735(ester, CO-O) ; 1375-(C-CH₃) ; 1026 (eq. acyl group).

Biological assay : All the compounds were tested against sarcoma-180 in strain A mice. Testing of compounds II, III, VI were carried out in KB cell culture, I, II and III against lymphoid leukemia L1210, and IV and VI against lymphocytic leukemia, P 388. None of the compounds, however, showed any activity to justify their development as useful drugs.

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